

Engineering Design Analysis (Physics of Failure)

Gary S. Drake, USAMSAA

Key Words: design-in reliability, Physics of Failure, failure mechanisms, fatigue, vibration, thermal overstress, shock

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

In December 2007, the Army Acquisition Executive approved the new Army Reliability Policy. The policy was developed to cost-effectively increase the reliability of Army systems. The new policy encourages use of cost-effective reliability best practices and provides a mechanism to alert key Army leaders when weapon systems are off track with respect to meeting their reliability requirements.

One of the policy's key elements is early engineering design in order to "design-in reliability." Physics of Failure (PoF) is a science-based approach to reliability that uses modeling and simulation to design-in reliability. The approach models the root causes of failure such as fatigue, fracture, wear and corrosion. PoF analyses are used to address long-term wear-out issues due to random vibration, thermal overstress or repetitive shock. Computer-Aided Design (CAD) tools have been developed to address various failure mechanisms and sites. Examples of failure mechanisms include things such as metal fractures on various vehicle components or fatigue cracking of electronic solder joints.

The US Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity (AMSAA) conducts PoF analyses to support contractors, program managers (PMs) and engineers on systems in all stages of acquisition from design, to test and evaluation (T&E) and fielded systems. In the design stage system level dynamics models, component finite element models and fatigue-life models are used to reveal the underlying physics of the hardware in its mission environment. Outputs of these analyses include forces acting on a system, displacements of components, accelerations, stress levels, weak points in the design and probable component life. This information is used during the design process to make design changes early in the acquisition process when it is easier and more cost effective.

Design decisions and corrective actions made early in the acquisition phase lead to improved efficiency and effectiveness of the T&E process. The intent is to make fixes prior to T&E which will reduce test time and cost, allow more information to be obtained from test, and improve test focus. PoF analyses can be conducted for failure occurring during test to better understand the underlying physics of the problem and identify the root cause of failures which leads to better fixes for problems discovered, reduced test-fix-test iterations and reduced decision risk. The same analyses and benefits mentioned above can be applied to systems which are exhibiting failures in the field.

1 INTRODUCTION

In December 2007, the Army Acquisition Executive established a new Reliability Policy. The policy was developed in response to data that showed a significant number of Army systems failing to demonstrate established reliability requirements. The goal is to cost-effectively increase the reliability of Army systems and encourage use of cost-effective reliability best practices. It provides a mechanism to alert key Army leaders when weapon systems are off track with respect to meeting their reliability requirements. One key element of this policy is to "design-in reliability." Physics of Failure (PoF) is a science-based approach to reliability that uses modeling and simulation to design-in reliability. The approach models root causes of failure such as fatigue, fracture, wear and corrosion. PoF analyses are used to address long-term wear-out issues due to random vibration, thermal overstress or repetitive shock. Computer-Aided Design (CAD) tools have been developed to address various failure mechanisms and sites. Examples of failure mechanisms include things such as metal fractures on various vehicle components or fatigue cracking of electronic solder joints.

AMSAA conducts PoF analysis to support contractors, PMs and engineers in all stages of acquisition from design, to T&E and fielded systems. In the design stage system level dynamics models, component finite element models and fatigue-life models are used to reveal the underlying physics of the hardware in its mission environment. Outputs of these analyses include forces acting on a system, displacements of components, accelerations, stress levels, weak points in the design and probably component life. This information is used during the design process to make design changes early in the acquisition process when it is easier and more cost effective.

Design decisions and corrective actions made early in the acquisition phase lead to improved efficiency and effectiveness of the T&E process. The intent is to make fixes prior to T&E which will reduce test time and cost, allow more information to be obtained from test, and improve test focus. PoF analyses can be conducted for failures occurring during test to better understand the underlying physics of the problem and identify the root cause of failures which leads to better fixes for problems discovered, reduced test-fix-test iterations and reduced decision risk. The same analyses and benefits mentioned above can be applied to systems which are exhibiting failures in the field.

2 PHYSICS OF FAILURE

AMSAA conducts both mechanical and electronics physics of failure. This paper will focus primarily on electronics PoF with a general discussion of mechanical PoF.

3 MECHANICAL PHYSICS OF FAILURE

Figure 1 graphically portrays a Mechanical PoF process overview.

Figure 1 –Mechanical PoF Process Overview

As indicated in Figure 1, we can either use results of system-level dynamics models or actual test data as input into finite element analysis (FEA) models. FEA is used to compute stress on mechanical components which is then fed into computational fatigue analysis models to predict component life. AMSAA is actively conducting PoF analysis for numerous contractors and PMs on systems in all stages of acquisition.

4 ELECTRONIC PHYSICS OF FAILURE

4.1 Overview

An electronic PoF analysis typically consists of a thermal analysis (system-level and/or board-level), Circuit Card Assembly (CCA) thermal overstress assessment, CCA shock response analysis, CCA shock response assessment, CCA modal analysis, CCA random vibration response analysis, CCA thermal and vibration fatigue life assessments, and a CCA thermal plated-through hole (PTH) fatigue analysis. The system-level thermal analysis determines the temperature of the internal air and the chassis walls. It provides boundary information for the CCA thermal analysis. The CCA thermal analysis determines the steady-state temperatures of all components based on the temperatures at the CCA boundaries and the power dissipated by each component when the system is energized. Each steady-state component temperature is compared to its manufacturer's rated temperature during the thermal overstress assessment. The CCA shock response determines the board displacement and strain due to a given shock pulse. During the CCA shock survivability assessment, the computed board displacement and strain are compared to an empirically-based maximum allowable out-of-plane

displacement and an acceptable board strain, respectively. The natural frequencies of a CCA are determined by the modal analysis. The CCA random vibration response analysis determines the displacement and curvature of a CCA due to random vibration loading. Based on input from the random vibration analysis and transportation/usage profile(s), the CCA vibration fatigue life assessment estimates the fatigue life of all component solder joints and leads on each CCA. The CCA thermal-fatigue life assessment determines each component's solder-joint life based on the number, magnitude, and duration of the thermal cycles (i.e., change in temperature due to powering on / powering down the equipment, change in temperature due to daily outside ambient temperature changes, etc.). The combined CCA thermal and vibration fatigue assessment predicts the fatigue life of all component solder joints and leads based on the cumulative damage due to vibration loading and thermal cycling. Finally, the CCA PTH fatigue analysis provides a life estimate of a PTH barrel in the CCA substrates based on the worst-case PTH geometry and the number, magnitude, and duration of the thermal cycles. See Figure 2 for an overview of the electronic PoF analysis process.

Figure 2 –Electronic PoF Process Overview

4.2 Environmental Characterization

It is very important to accurately model the environment in which the equipment will be operating. The environment is broken down into five parts within the circuit card assemblies' life cycle: Manufacture/Maintenance, Shipping/Handling, Environmental Stress Screening, Transportation, and Operation/Mission Usage. Each produces different exposure levels and durations. The Manufacture/Maintenance, Shipping/Handling, and Environmental Stress Screening stages include all the stress cycles that the CCA experiences while being manufactured, handled in the factory, and screened for weak components. The Transportation stage includes the transportation of the circuit card assemblies from the factory to the field, where they are permanently installed in the end-use vehicle. Negligible fatigue damage is assumed in these four stages. The Operation/Mission Usage stage includes all damage accumulated due to operating the equipment in the field and is where most damage occurs. Therefore, the analyses only consider damage accumulated in the final stage.

The operation/mission usage is generally described in the Operation Mode Summary/Mission Profile (OMS/MP). The OMS/MP will provide annual operating time under vibration and annual number of equipment on/off cycles. The values in this table would be selected to most accurately estimate the vibration exposure levels on the CCAs being analyzed. See Figure 3 for an example of vibration exposure levels. Both Peacetime and Wartime vibrations would be considered annually. Furthermore, the exposure levels can be evaluated for both move and idle operations.

Figure 3 – Platform Vibration Exposure Levels

Shock exposure levels are based on the Air Drop values given by the manufacturer, and the functional shock and crash values given in MIL-STD-810F. See Table 1 for an example of shock exposure levels.

	Peak Value (g's)	Nominal Duration (ms)
Air Drop	18	95
Functional 1	25	11
Functional 2	45	9
Crash	80	5

Table 1 – Shock Exposure Levels

A daily temperature cycle of 17°C is generally used in all thermal solder-joint fatigue calculations. The temperature cycle is based on the ambient temperature fluctuations of a hot-dry climate per Army Regulation 70-38.

The maximum outside ambient temperature is typically assumed to be 49°C per AR70-38.

4.3 Software

All analyses are performed using MathCAD version 14 (commercially-available general purpose equation solver/plotter), ANSYS ICEPAK version 4.4.6, MSC.Patran/Nastran version 2005r2 (commercially-available general purpose Finite-Element Analysis (FEA) package), macros written in Microsoft Excel 2003, and the University of Maryland's CalcePWA software version 5.

ICEPAK is a fully interactive, object-based, thermal management software tool, used for thermal management by design engineers in the electronics industry. The ICEPAK design environment allows engineers to predict air flow and heat transfer at the component-level, board-level, or cabinet-level, to reduce design costs and time-to-market of high-performance electronic systems. ICEPAK uses the ANSYS solver engine, FLUENT to provide complete flexibility in modeling complex geometries on unstructured mesh. ICEPAK utilizes Computational Fluid Dynamics and Heat transfer principles to simulate thermal performance of electronic systems and to determine the temperature of the electronic systems.

CalcePWA is a full-featured and fully-independent software package developed and maintained by the Center for Advanced Life Cycle Engineering (CALCE) at the University of Maryland. It has a Printed Wiring Board (PWB) design module for modeling the CCA substrates and a thermal analysis module that uses control volume theory. It also has finite-difference methods to determine the CCA temperature profile; a vibration analysis module that uses laminate plate theory and finite-element techniques to determine CCA natural frequency, displacement, and curvature; and life profile / failure analysis modules that provide reliability assessments. The algorithms implemented within the software are based on existing scientific knowledge that has been assembled through review of textbooks, published articles, and research conducted by the CALCE group.

4.4 Modeling the CCA

The first step in the electronic PoF process is to develop a detailed model of the CCA using CalcePWA. In order to do this engineering drawings and associated parts lists and part information are necessary. CCA dimensions and board materials are modeled. Printed Wiring Board drawings that include overall dimensions, drill plan (including plated through hole/via sizes, locations, plating thickness, plating material, fill, etc.), and layer information (number of layers, layer thickness, total thickness, dielectric layer material, percentage of copper on each layer, etc.) are also needed. More detailed information allows for a much more accurate model of the CCA. Figure 4 shows a component placement

Figure 4 – Component Placement Drawing

Figure 5– CalcePWA Model

drawing of a CCA, and Figure 5 shows the CalcePWA model of the same board

It is very important to model the board constraints, i.e. how the board is fastened to the chassis. Figure 6 shows the simple supports for the CCA shown above. They are simply supported screws which attach the CCA to the chassis.

Figure 6– CalcePWA Model with CCA Supports

4.5 Modal and Random Vibration Response Analysis

CCA modal and random vibration response analyses are performed on each board to determine its first three natural frequencies and maximum displacement under the random vibration loading as specified for the analysis. The analysis results are used as inputs to shock and vibration fatigue life assessments. Lower dynamic displacements, which generally result from higher natural frequencies, are more desirable than higher displacements. An example of modal analysis results is displayed in Table 2.

Also computed is the random vibration dynamic displacement. An example of random displacement is shown in Figure 7.

Mode	1	2	3
Frequency (Hz)	269	454	553

Table 2 – Natural Frequencies and Respective Mode Shapes

Figure 7– Random Vibration Dynamic Displacement

obtained from thermal analysis or test measurements. They are entered into CalcePWA. Figure 8 depicts results from thermal analysis and how they are mapped into CalcePWA.

Figure 8– Thermal Analysis Boundary Conditions

Thermal overstress analysis will use the results of the thermal analysis and mapping to the components on the CCA to determine which component temperatures exceed manufacturers rated temperatures.

4.6 Shock Response and Survivability Assessment

A CCA shock response analysis is performed on each board to determine its displacement and maximum strain due to the shock pulses. The CCA shock survivability assessment compares the maximum displacement and strain to an empirically-based maximum allowable out-of-plane displacement and acceptable board strain. The results are given in likelihood of failure. Table 3 is an example of shock analysis results.

Event / Measure	Maximum Board Displacement (mm)	Maximum Board Curvature X (1/mm)	Maximum Board Curvature Y (1/mm)	Maximum Board Strain X (micro strain)	Maximum Board Strain Y (micro strain)
Shock Event Half-Sine 19.5 G's @ 100 ms	1.291E-01	1.736E-04	3.156E-04	133.2	242.1
Shock Event Half-Sine 20 G's @ 11 ms	1.324E-01	1.781E-04	3.237E-04	136.6	248.3
Shock Event Half-Sine 40 G's @ 9 ms	2.776E-01	3.646E-04	6.762E-04	279.6	518.6
Shock Event Half-Sine 75 G's @ 5 ms	7.486E-01	9.266E-04	1.783E-03	710.7	1367.6

Table 3– Shock Analysis Results

4.7 Vibration Fatigue Life Assessment

The vibration fatigue assessment models provide an estimate of the fatigue life for CCA component interconnects (e.g., solder joints and component leads) based on input from the vibration analysis and transportation/usage profile(s). Failures occur due to stresses developed in the leads and solder-joints from the difference in relative curvature of the components and PWB and from in-plane accelerations acting on the components. Relative curvature and in-plane accelerations continually change based on the input vibration (random and/or harmonic) load. The resulting stress fluctuations cause interconnect fatigue.

The results are given in terms of Damage Ratio (DR). The DR is the ratio of the actual number of cycles over a lifetime divided by the number of cycles that will cause failure. A DR greater than 1 indicates failure. Figure 9 depicts the results of vibration fatigue life assessment on a CCA.

4.8 Thermal Fatigue Life Assessment

The thermal solder-joint fatigue assessment model provides an estimate of the fatigue life for CCA component interconnects (i.e., solder-joints). Failures occur due to Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) mismatch between the PWB and components. As the temperature goes up (or down), a component expands less than or greater than the PWB. The difference in expansion induces strain on the solder joints. The strain varies as temperature varies.

Repeated, varying strain on the solder joints causes interconnect fatigue. Figure 10 depicts the results of a thermal fatigue life assessment.

Figure 9– Vibration Fatigue Life Assessment

Figure 10– Thermal Fatigue Life Assessment

4.9 Combined Fatigue Life Assessment

The combined fatigue life assessment model provides an estimate of the fatigue life for CCA component interconnects (e.g., solder-joints and component leads) based on concurrent vibration (due to relative board curvature) and thermal loading (in-plane). The model utilizes Miner's rule of cumulative damage (i.e., accumulated damage is equal to the sum of the damage due to vibration and damage due to thermal cycling). Figure 11 depicts the results of a combined fatigue life assessment.

Figure 11– Combined Fatigue Life Assessment

Design decisions and corrective actions made early in the acquisition process are generally easier to make and much more cost effective. This also leads to improved efficiency and effectiveness in the test and evaluation process.

BIOGRAPHY

Gary S. Drake
Operations Research Analyst, USAMSAA
ATTN: AMSRD-AMS-LA
392 Hopkins Road
APG, MD 21005-5017

Gary Drake is Team Leader of the Electronics Physics of Failure Team at the U.S. Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity. He earned his bachelor's degree in Mathematics at the University of Maryland and his master's degree in Administrative Science at the Johns Hopkins University.